

Islamic Views on the Political Processes and the Quest for Good Governance in Nigeria

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Abstract

It is not an understatement that Nigeria since independence six decades ago is yet to witness standard political processes that will eventually produce good governance. The political class that came after the reigns of Nigerian political founding fathers comprises of people from at least the two major religions; Islam and Christianity like their predecessors. The sources of these religions out-rightly teach leadership and qualities of good governance. The primary sources of Islam; Qur'ān and Sunnah contain number of injunctions that implore not only Muslim leaders, but anyone assigned with governance through legal process to be upright and serves as role model for the followers. It has been found that, many Nigerian political leaders attained various political positions through corrupt processes, hence in opposite to their religious beliefs, therefore led to poor governance. This paper adopted empirical approach and qualitative method with scriptural analysis to proffer solutions that can probably restore the use of real political processes through which good governance could be actualized. The paper then suggests that Muslims among our political class should showcase the exact political thought of Islam where leaders are accountable not only to the populace, but also to Allah. It also advised all political stakeholders to be transparent, and lead by example, to enhance politics of inclusion.

Keywords: Governance, Islamic view, Leadership, Political Processes, Quest

Introduction

Nigeria and its heterogeneous condition from time immemorial has bounded the all and sundry in the country to differ in focus, purpose and objectives. The political history of the country for years back is yet to make a good record, despite the popularity, capacity and endowment features in the line of committee of nations in Africa and the world at large. Right from independence through the years of republicanism to the present moment, same quest for good governance is still the song from the masses. Political office holders in Nigeria even though claiming to belong to one religion or the other only proclaim this to achieve power and later abandon the ethics and teachings of its contents. According to Paramole, political leaders in Nigeria only use religion as a means to political ends, if not, they must have considered their individual religious ethics as 'a matrix upon which leadership could be masses oriented.'¹ Precisely, this attitude does not allow them to showcase the teachings of their proclaimed religion in leadership and this eventually dashed the hope of citizens in their quest for good governance.

Apparently, Nigeria political system is characterized by poor governance which continues to demoralize well-meaning people to partake in the public political processes. Due to some outcomes of poor governance, the country lacks effective and efficient mechanisms that can ensure outstanding development in a growing environment. Sulaimon Adigun and Sagie Narsiah expounded the factors that responsible for poor governance and the end results in Nigeria. They mentioned lack of confidence in the political class, corruption in political processes, ethnicity, gender inequality, status discrimination in the political organizations, among others; while all these and many more brought about poverty, disinterest in political processes, poor social and economic conditions, political disenfranchisement and so on.² The lack of good governance in Nigeria since independence and first republic results to challenge of reforms in all spheres of human endeavors while all efforts to proffer solutions are always in vain. There is no doubt that, the assessment made by the Transparency International in the years back on Nigeria could be truer; to be ranked third among the 102 most corrupt countries due to growth of

unemployment with over 40% urban youth jobless, two third of the citizens in poverty and enormous political challenges.³ It is felt that, the situation is getting worse every day with no sign of renaissance.

It is as a result of the above that, large number of Nigerians are clamoring for good governance, though small number are able to participate in the political processes due to factors mentioned earlier. The bastardized political processes do not promote the country, rather draw it back. However, Islam through its primary and secondary sources has antidotes to the poisons in the Nigerian political processes. The political theory of Islam with its major sources (Qur'an and Sunnah) establishes principles that guide towards promoting good governance and hitch free political processes.⁴

This work focuses on the position of Islam towards the processes through which Nigerian political system is been practiced. Even though, democracy to many is regarded as the best means of governance, yet the Nigerian political practitioners proved it wrong and made it to be addressed as dirty game. Hopefully, if the Islamic guidelines are followed and adopted for Nigerian political processes, the quest for good governance will not be a fruitless effort and citizens' expectations from the government will not be dashed.

Conceptual Clarification

Islamic View: Every society is made up of certain practices and beliefs which the people therein accept to be positive and be of great value to them. At the same time, anything regarded as negative and has no value to them shall always be addressed as such. Islamic view concerns the perspective at which the Qur'an and *Sunnah* recognize every aspect of human endeavors. There are rules, principles and guidance for Muslims on all daily activities apart from the spiritual duties which is between them and Allah (SWT). Islam guides Muslims on *Mu'amalat* (human relationships): economically, politically, socially and morally. All aforementioned are catered for in *Shari'ah* (Islamic law) purposely to fulfill the well-being and good inter-relationships among mankind. Therefore, Islam provides for establishment, reformation and revival of human society.

Leadership: Leadership in a simple meaning is an ability to direct, supervise, control, inspire, guide, protect, organize and encourage others who directly or indirectly rely on one's wisdom and experience to achieve a set of objectives at a point in time. According to Paramole, citing Olusoji asserting that, leadership has to do with rising to the organization and coordination of resources, relationships, skills, expertise and finances to achieve a common goal for the common good of all.⁵ In a nutshell, leadership is all about knowledge and skills that will tirelessly work towards the wellbeing of the people in a given society. Accordingly, Yakan views leadership as the art of dealing with human nature and influencing human behavior and guiding it towards a specific goal and in such a way as to secure obedience to it, confidence in it and to it.⁶

Allah (SWT) makes it clear that in every situation, someone will be mostly blessed than and ahead of others in the way He has elevated His Prophets over the rest of mankind, and also singled out Muhammad (SAW) as the best of mankind according to the Qur'an. (Q2:253) (Q68:4) Therefore, leadership is divine because Allah (SWT) is the Originator, therefore, every leader whether religious or not, is a vicegerent of Allah.⁷

Political Processes: According to *Merriam-Webster Unabridged Dictionary*, political process as noun is the process of the formulation and administration of public policy usually by interaction between social groups and political institutions or between political leadership and public opinion.⁸ In relevance to this work, political processes include the followings: nomination of someone to run or running in an election for a political position, voting for someone or removal of a political office holder, signing relevant petition against a political officer, seeking election or appointment to a political standing committee, or seeking to be a political delegate and many more that concern political considerations.

Quest: Relevant hypernyms for 'Quest' in this work are: asking for; expressing the need or desire for something or someone; the act of searching for someone or something of benefits or great/adding values etc. In the Cambridge Dictionary, quest means a long search for something that is difficult to find, or an attempt to achieve something difficult.⁹ Oxford dictionary states thus: "a long search for something (happiness, knowledge, truth etc.), especially for some qualities."¹⁰ The above similar meanings could be lights towards agreeing that, quest

for something could be endless, because man will always search for better condition than the one he finds himself. Likewise, every society will eventually be in need of reforms, progress, improvement or development. Therefore, quest is an unlimited adventure, desire and act of clamoring for better living in an organized environment. Relevantly, the search towards having right-type of Nigerians to be in-charge of political processes and governance of Nigeria cannot be underrated.

Good Governance: According to Makinde, citing the Board of Independence Advocacy Project's definition of good governance as a political and institutional environment based on respect for democratic principles, the rule of law, human rights and the participation of civil society.¹¹ He added that, it is only by good governance that there can be exercise of effective, honest, equitable, transparent and accountable power at the various levels of government.¹² In fact, it is through the aforementioned that a country achieves responsible and responsive economic and financial management of public and natural resources for economic and social advancement with sustainable and equitable reduction of poverty.

Background to the Study: An insight to Undue Political Processes and Poor Governance in Nigeria

For decades now, Nigeria despite been the largest black nation of Africa could not boast of reliable, responsible and responsive government. This is due to ineffective and inefficient of various political reforms and agenda. All efforts put in place to normalize the system proved abortive, may be due to insincerity of the people in-charge or the faulty of the policies designed. There are many factors behind this, according to Abdullahi Yusuf Usman who states thus:

By the time Nigeria won her independence from Britain in 1960, its artificial origin, coupled with other factors, had bequeathed it a number of fundamental problems, one of which is the challenge of integrating, into a cohesive socio-political whole, various entities and strange bed fellows that were lumped together by the colonialists.¹³

The above statement shows clearly that, the origin of untidy political processes and poor governance in Nigeria could be traced to era before and after independence. This is a country where people avoid social interaction with other castes with reflections in the attitude of politicians and their loyalists during the period of political processes. Hence, poor governance takes the day due to nepotism, resentment and hostility among different political stakeholders.

According to Uzoh, majority of Nigerian political processes and those who champion governance in the country are malevolent. He addressed Nigerian politics and stressed his assertion about Political processes and governance in the country with words of Hyden and Bratton that poor governance is same with bad politics: "a self-aggravated management of the public realm, the end result of which is parasitic encroachment, waste and overall impoverishment."¹⁴ He further states some of the features of Nigerian political processes and governance as extensive personalization of political power, the denial of fundamental human rights, widespread corruption and prevalence of unelected and unaccountable government.¹⁵ Without argument, this work concurs that, all the above and many more caused Nigerians to be governed by uncaring government with disrespect to public interests.

The expectations of many Nigerians from the return of Democracy in 1999 has been dashed, as the country continues to experience problems of insecurity, corruption, prodigious internal and external debts, mass unemployment, high rate of poverty, irregular power supply, deteriorating infrastructure, malfunctioning of government institutions, multiple rigging in electoral processes, political and character assassinations, injustice, disrespect for rule of law among others, to mention but a few.

All the above mentioned are scholarly perused by Elesin, while addressing causes of failure of the government in Nigeria. In addition, he pointed at misapplication of Nigerian Cultural values norms while in public positions as of great damage to governance in the country. Many political or public office holders regard such positions as birthright rather than privilege and therefore, misbehave and ended seeing the office as a mean of enriching themselves and family members.¹⁶ Another observation is made on the enforcement agencies. For instance,

Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) is to conduct and ensure free and fair elections across the country. Mostly the institution is overwhelmed with the parade of politicians and their political parties' gifts and bribes which eventually lead them to undermining their national assignment to conduct credible and hitch free elections. In 2023 general elections and subsequent ones, cases of vote buying, multiple voting, under-age voting, ballot box snatching, inconclusive elections and so on were the major challenges of political processes. Meanwhile, compromise towards credible elections with influence of money is no doubt the key to poor governance. Other agencies like State Security Service (SSS), National Intelligence Agency (NIA), Election Tribunal Courts mostly failed to help affirmation of electoral justice. This is also in line with the reports of Eleshin¹⁷ and Uzoh who added that, all these are happening due to inability of political parties to articulate policies that respond to benefit the masses, rather securing themselves the highest financial returns.¹⁸

Despite the desire of millions of Nigerians and loud requests for good governance and credible political processes that will ensure effective and efficient stability of all societal facets for years, the beginning of fourth republic in 1999 supposed to have brought an end to the hardship experience of the citizens. Yet, corruption and bad leadership by unpatriotic politicians make the system worse than ever before. This assertion is favorably in support of Dahunsi and Omotoso while citing Justice Bolasodun Ajigbola in his statement that: "Corruption has been democratized in Nigeria."¹⁹

Political and economic reforms, and policies have been favorable only to the political class at the expense of the common Nigerians. For instance, creation of mid-western region by NPC and NCNC coalition government in 1963 was a game of continuous domination of a particular region on others. Even though with claim that, it is a framework towards ease of governance yet, the argument made by Adejuyigbe (1989) could not be opposed, if such has brought good end result as critically studied.²⁰ Same motive was behind the creation of States by successive Military regimes since 1967 to 1996 which was either to legitimize long stay in governance, favor their kinsmen or as a pay-back to eminent persons.

Economically, bad political processes also earned Nigeria poor governance that apparently lead the country to weakened economy. Dahunsi and Omotoso discuss about how Nigerian economic linkage was fragmented by both Military and Civilian governments as one of the features of poor governance. They point out that, the extractive nature of the country's economy that was based on the colonial political economy brought about challenges. Even though, various National Development Plans were put in place to rehabilitate, reconstruct and reconcile the political and economic situation of the country since the end of civil war in 1975, yet loss of focus made the government failed and turned Nigeria to a dependent economy, despite the oil boom.²¹ By the above summary, the genesis of poor economy is poor governance, with massive importation of goods and neglect of agricultural exports that has largest percentage of economic resources. Hence, Nigerian economy became dominated by foreign monopoly capital markets, including gradual and total inactiveness of Nigerian refineries.²²

In a nutshell, scholars that have studied political history and governance conclude that, a stable Nigeria can only be realized when the following are given due status in the running of the country's affairs, namely; clear political participation, transparency, accountability, respect for the rule of law, responsiveness, justice, fairness, equity, decentralization of governance, combating corruption and poverty reduction.²³ However, leadership could not only be the agent of bad political processes and poor governance, except with the backing of poor followership. In the years back, it has been observed that, ignorance (about human rights, human dignity, rule of law, etc.), lack of self-defense, and poverty are the factors responsible for citizens; hence encouraged bad political processes and poor governance, as in Nigeria. It is with the above that Elesin's arguments were accepted as thus: "From the part of the followers, a lot of irregularities are also recorded from them. Such defects include engaging in bribery practices, compromising one's right and future, for quick money...."²⁴

One could attribute this negative attitude of the citizens to frustration experienced through the inhuman behavior of the leaders. Automatically, despondent feelings of the citizens lead to compromising their rights for illegal material gains. In fact, this has also led to negligent act towards electoral processes which is an indirect sabotaging Political progress and encouraging poor governance. Some other factors that cause bad political

processes and poor governance as opined by scholars and highlighted are: poor reward system (that is, imbalance between obligation and qualification; and where no conventional appreciation for voluntary goodness but punishment for offences), poor administration of legal and judicial system, religious intolerance, among others.²⁵ Other factors include: the denial of fundamental human rights, widespread corruption and prevalence of unelected and unaccountable government, greediness, dishonesty, insincerity and self-centeredness.²⁶

Based on the foregoing, one may out-rightly conclude that, Nigerian political freedom could not measure up to meeting the reality of time over the years, especially since the beginning of the forth republic in 1999. This is nothing but the negative effect of bad political processes and poor governance. It is indeed necessary to say that, Islam as an all-encompassing religion has standard principles that by assurance, if sincerely adopted for Nigerian political processes and governance, will definitely make the long good dream of the citizens be fulfilled.

Features of Political Processes and Good Governance: Islamic Perspective

Going by historical observations, one could agree with the words of Makinde that goes thus: “There is a lot of problem facing governance in Nigeria. Inability to have a good governance has made the country and its citizens to face enormous challenges politically and economically.”²⁷ This is an affirmation of our earlier discussions on the subject matter. Among our findings is that, many political and economic reforms were introduced and promulgated, yet the country could not balance rather getting more deteriorating. In an overview, every factor that makes good governance and good political process in any given society is Islamic and permissible. As Islam encourages all factors that could bring well-being and progressive development to the society. There are models in Islam for political system and governance of the people by their leaders. Governance in Islam is a trust that must be duly accorded respect under the tenet of Allah’s law and the practice of His Prophet (SAW). This opinion is in agreement with the view of Paramole: “leadership in Islam is based upon sound spiritual and moral foundations and as well by divine instructions.”²⁸ There are some main terms that make Islamic leadership or political practice of Islam differs from other systems of government, namely;

Tawhid: Belief in the supremacy, unity and oneness of Allah. This signifies the unity of the people in government and citizens. Then intention towards common goal must be paramount in their political processes. One of the numerous verses of the Qur’an that points out oneness of God and His absolute power on everything states thus: “...and there is not any deity except Allah, the One, the Prevailing. Lord of the heavens and the earth and whatever is between them, the Exalted in Might, the Perpetual Forgiver.” (Q38:65-66) The verse reminds us about the unbeatable control that Allah has over the government and the governed.

Sovereignty belongs to Allah and not to the people: That the rulers do not have power to make decisions while the citizens have no opinion that superior than that of Allah (SWT). Choosing, electing, selecting or removal of the leader must be in accordance with the directives of Allah and His messenger. This indicates what differs Islamic political theory from other political ideologies where sovereignty lies with; the few people (oligarchy), majority of the people (democracy), king or queen (monarchy), a dictator with no room for opposition (totalitarianism), small class of privileged individuals (aristocracy) and so on. All the above mentioned are meant to be modified by Islam in principle that, sovereignty and power belongs to Allah as rightly established in the Qur’an: “Say! O Allah, Owner of sovereignty, You give sovereignty to whom You will and you take sovereignty away from whom You will...” (Q3:26)

Pattern of Leadership as set by the Prophet and the *Khulafau r-Rashidun*: It is only by emulating the Prophet (SAW) that one claims to have understood Allah’s directives. The *Khulafau r-Rashidun* (Rightly Guided Caliphs) who represented the prophet intensified on the obedience to Allah and His messenger, and they led by example. They were enough for every political leader to be emulated in the choosing of leaders, executing political decisions and as well governing of the people. The Prophet (SAW) emphasized on the significance of following his practice in all human endeavors with leadership style inclusive. He added the purity of those who took mantle of leadership after him, majorly the *Khulafau r-Rashidun* in his saying: “...So you must keep to (the use) of my Sunnah (practice) and the practice of the rightly-guided caliphs.”²⁹

Khilafah: This is the principle of vicegerency. Everyone must be aware that he or she is representing Allah in any capacity of governance, from lower to the highest cadre. Therefore, the best available personality in moral, spiritual and intellectual must be nominated, chosen or elected to govern. There are number of verses of the Qur'an that intensify the intent of Allah for making man His vicegerent on earth:

- i. His decision was made known to angels to make upon the earth a successive authority: (Q2:30)
- ii. He (Allah) put it straight to mankind that He makes them the authority on earth to act on His behalf: (Q27:62)
- iii. What pleases Allah most is to have sincere believer and righteous person in the position of authority: (Q24:55)
- iv. It is expected for anyone in the position of authority that, he is representing Allah. Prophet Dawud (AS) was instructed to govern with justice and warned his heart desires: (Q38:26).

All the above verses explicitly signify the position of authority holding by man as temporary that is still subjected to power and decisions of Allah, the All-Powerful and Controlling. In addition, such leader is representing Allah on earth in coordinating the affairs of his people and he is expected to do justice among them.

Amanah: This is the principle of Trust. This assist even the political leader to do self-assessment with check and balances. There must be guidelines to ensure strict adherence of the leader and followers to the laws of Allah on matters that concern governance and political processes. The Prophet (SAW) guides us in his sayings: "Every one of you is a shepherd and so shall be responsible for his herd."³⁰ The principle of Trust necessitates the establishment of *Mas-uliyyah* (Accountability). With this, leaders are accountable to both Allah and the followers. Citizens have due right to receive report of affairs from those in the authority. It is from principles of *Amanah* and *Mas-uliyyah* that Islam affirms excellence in governance because upholding both signifies strict adherence to the commandments of Allah: "Indeed, Allah commands you to render trusts to whom they are due and when you judge between people to judge with justice..." (Q4:58) From the above verse, governance with justice (*Adl*) is also one of the major features of Islamic Political system. That is why Prophet Dawud (AS) was instructed to judge or govern with justice. Therefore, it is very clear that, the trio of *Amanah*, *Mas-uliyyah* and *Adl* are factors that cannot be underrated in the Islamic Political theory or governance.

Shura: This is the principle that guides the process of consultation. There should be room for public opinion and counseling that will be within the framework of Allah's directives and the teachings of His messenger. Here, there is room for consensus between the leader and his subjects. The principle of *Shura* is also exercised during electoral activities by willingly showing interest in voting for someone or to be voted for without compromise, fear or favor. It also covers right to freedom of expression for the citizens without the option of life and death as we have it today.

It is through *Shura* that public interest and freedom of expression are achieved either by verbal expression, body expression or total denouncement of the situation by not partaking in undue activities from citizenship perspective. This is in accordance to the Hadith: "Whoever among you sees evil (in the society), let him change it with his hand. If he cannot do so, then with his tongue. If he cannot do so, then with his heart, which is the weakest level of faith."³¹

At-Ta'ah: This means obedience. Islam encourages obedience to the constituted authority. This is compulsory in as much the instructions or directives given are not leading to disobeying Allah or committing of prohibition. This has been emphasized in the Qur'an: "O you who have believed, obey Allah and obey the messenger and those in authority among you. And if you disagree over anything, refer it to Allah and His messenger..." (Q4:59) It is deduced from the verse that, even obedience to the people of authority has limitation, as it was also buttressed by the Prophet (SAW) to have said: "To listen and obey is a must or compulsory duty, in as much one is not commanded to criminality, but if someone is commanded to commit criminality, there should be no listening nor obedience."³²

The Prophet (SAW) further said: "I counsel you to have *Taqwa* (fear of Allah), and listen and obey (your leader), even if a slave were to become your commander..."³³ All the above are the major features of Islamic

Political theory with emphasis on working towards good governance. The number of the features of Islamic Political System may differ among the scholars, yet sovereignty of Allah, *Tawhid*, *Khilafah*, *Shurah*, *'Adl* and *Mas-uliyyah* are absolutely the main foundations, due to their divinity in nature.

Islamic Views on Political Processes and Governance in Nigeria.

Voting Exercise representing *Bay'ah* (Oath of Allegiance). Islam duly recommend people's allegiance for a Political leader before he could fully assume the leadership office. Pledge of allegiance and agreement were made by people of Yathrib (Madinah) before the migration of the Prophet and they entrusted him with the leadership of the city that eventually transformed to Islamic State. The *Khulafau r-Rashidun* also had the oath of allegiance and vote of confidence from the people. Political leadership has to be by people's consent unlike Nigerian context, where Democratic process is full of irregularities that are totally alien in Islamic political theory.

In the Qur'anic verse that emphasizes on *bay'ah*, Allah says: "Indeed, those who pledge allegiance to you, (O Muhammad) - they are actually pledging allegiance to Allah. The hand of Allah is over their hands. So he who breaks his word only breaks it to the detriment of himself. And he who fulfill that which he has promised Allah - He will give him a great reward." (Q48:10). The verse lays emphasis on fulfilling voting rights with sincerity, while the one seeking political office should also fulfill electoral promises. Therefore, both the people voting and the persons voted should showcase sense of political responsibility. Every citizen that collect bribe to vote and candidate giving it during elections, including corrupt judges of electoral tribunal should not expect the governance to be favorable but aggressive and deceitful. The prohibition of bribery in all matters is clearly stated in the Qur'an: (Q2:188 and the Prophet (SAW) was reported thus: "The curse of Allah is upon the one who offers a bribe and the one who takes it."³⁴

Furthermore, attitudes of bribery in election tribunals is the highest degree of corruption, and detrimentally the negative effect of installing bad politicians cannot be escaped by them and their associates in crime. In their views, they boast of doing the country a good favor but rather it is an act of indignity. This view is tactically deduced from the verse: "And when it is said to them, "Do not cause corruption on the earth," they say, "We are but reformers." Unquestionably, it is they who are the corrupters, but they perceive (it) not." (Q2:12) The verse above implies that, those who disrupt electoral activities in Nigeria are destroying the quest of millions of Nigeria for good governance. Because, holding political power by unelected people brings nothing than poor governance.

Modern scholars in Islamic and conventional political thoughts for years have same views on features of good governance. Some of the features as mentioned by Makinde (2012) are: freedom of political participation, accountability, responsiveness, transparency, effective and efficient institutions, rule of law, Consensus and justice.³⁵ Uzoh also added that, good governance requires special demands from the ruler and the citizens. He further outlined the demands for good governance from the followers or citizens, namely; obedience or loyalty, commitment, positive critical thinking, perseverance, etc.³⁶ From his points of view, we share his opinions with that of Islam by distinctly making it clear that, good governance is not only the responsibility of the political office holders and their parties but a joint effort to be supported by the citizens. (Q16:90)

Even though, in the principle of Islamic political theory, more emphases are laid on the leaders as Makinde³⁷ and Paramole³⁸ share same view that leaders are to always act as servants to their people, yet the roles of followers cannot be undermined. Because it is with the cooperation of the people that a righteous leader attain success and deliver diligently. (Q48:18). The positions of accountability and transparency in governance in Islam are side by side. Caliphs Abu Bakr and Umar were ever the worthiest of emulation after the Prophet (SAW) among his representatives when it comes to transparent and accountable government. It is highly disappointing for Nigerian leaders concealing many facts about their governance and at the same time use the position of authority to enrich themselves while millions are suffering. Edemode (2003) cited one Hadith narrated by 'Ad bin Amir Al-Kindi that keenly addresses the need to be transparent and accountable by leaders: "I heard the Messenger of Allah (SAW) saying: "Whosoever from you is appointed by us to a position of authority and conceals from us a needle or something smaller than that it would be misappropriation (of public funds) and he will (have to) produce (it)

on the Day of Judgement.”³⁹ ‘Umar bn Khattab and ‘Umar bn ‘Abdul-‘Azeez were known for accountability and transparency as entrenched by Islam and contributed a lot to economic stability and adequate management of public amenities during their reigns.⁴⁰

In addition, Islam opposes all forms of unethical political attitudes like; electoral malpractices, assassination, certificate forgery, threatening, kidnapping, rioting etc., because all these oppose protection of lives and properties, which is one of the objectives of *Shari’ah*. Apparently, Islamic Political Theory has outlined the features of those to be allowed in politics and governance with the directive of the Qur’an: “They are those who, if we appointed them as rulers on earth, they would establish the Contact Prayers (Salat) and the obligatory charity (*Zakat*), and would advocate righteousness and forbid evil. God is the Ultimate Ruler.” (Q22:41)

Matters on the Rule of Law: It is obvious that, rule of law in Nigeria is just on paper not in practicality. In the conventional political theory, the rule of law is the tool to guide against arbitrary government, where rulers and the ruled must be subjects to the law of the land in the constitution. In fact, the major features of the rule of law are; fundamental human rights, equality before the law and supremacy of the constitution. We share same opinion with Raheem (2004) that, rule of law in Nigeria is not properly practiced.⁴¹ The idea of sacred cow and immunity before the law has jeopardized good governance.

Islam establishes rule of law by making the ruler and the ruled to be equally treated. The Prophet (SAW) discourage inequality in his sayings: “The generations before you were destroyed because they used to inflict punishments on the lower class and forgive the higher class. By Him whose hand my soul. If Fatima (daughter of the Prophet) did that, I would cut off her hand.” This statement was made when people were pleading on behalf of a well-to-do woman that committed theft.⁴² ‘Umar bn Khattab was reported to have appeared before a court judge and likewise any governor or official under his government, while investigations and sanctions were done appropriately.⁴³ The matter surrounding rule of law is explicitly stated in the Qur’an: “O you who have believed, be persistently standing firm in justice, witnesses for Allah, even if it be against yourselves or parents and relatives. Whether one is rich or poor, Allah is more worthy of both. So follow not (personal) inclination, lest you not be just. And if you distort (your testimony) or refuse (to give it), then indeed Allah is ever, with what you do, Acquainted.” (Q4:135)

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing, it is necessary to state useful recommendations that possibly if adopted could actually facelift the political processes and governance in Nigeria, where people therein will be protected, peaceful, trustworthy and contended.

1. Muslims among politicians and their supporters need to rise towards showcasing leadership guided by the Divine. Various sources of Islam are enough for them, not only to study but also operationalize them in their political activities and governance. The conclusion of both Paramole⁴⁴ and Makinde⁴⁵ on the adoption of Islamic political practices is highly recommended.
2. The use of Qur’an or other holy book for swearing-in when assuming political offices should be discouraged as nothing good come out of it, except hypocrisy and unfulfilled promises. Divinely, this action also contributes to encountering the wrath of God not only on the failed political leaders but the entire people in the country as stated in the Qur’an: “*And fear a trial that which will not strike those who have wronged among you exclusively, and know that Allah is severe in penalty.*” (Q8:25)
3. Equality before the law and fair dealings should be adopted in governance and judgement. Shunning the courts of law when invited which has been habitual attitude of political leader represents bad political processes and poor governance. This work supports that, immunity should be removed from the country’s constitution as recommended by contemporary scholars. Al-Mallah states features needed in correspondence to this: equality between citizens in the eyes of law and all legislative acts; equality in matters of justice and in the courts of law; equality between all citizens in matters of taxation; and equality to public honors and offices of employment.⁴⁶

4. It is incumbent that; a democratic government of all-inclusiveness be adopted. Based on this reason, this work shares the views of Edemode when stating features of democratic government as follows: people-centeredness, principles of popular participation and representation, separation of powers, unfettered judiciary, open discussion of issues and procedural preferences in trinity.⁴⁴ However, the last of the features is the only one that has opposite status to Islamic tenet, meanwhile, sovereignty of Allah is the most suitable word in the view of Islam.

Summary and Conclusion

This work has showcased the study of political process and governance in Nigeria through brief historical survey. It has been found that, insensitivity on the part of the founding fathers of politics from the first and second republics paved way for Military governments concurrently. The arbitrary use of political power by the Military Junta later woke up Nigerians from slumber towards campaigning for democracy and good governance. But unfortunately, the bastardized political processes did not help the matter. Hence, all political reviews and reforms introduced could not assist to make a better Nigeria. This work therefore proffered some of Islamic views that if adopted can be of great advantage for the people of the country regardless of religion, ethnicity or class. In conclusion, adopting Islamic political ideology for Nigeria will be fruitfully responsive to the quests for good governance and hitch free political processes.

Endnotes

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- ⁴*Ibid.*, 15.
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